

Socio-Emotional Intelligence Enhancement: Experiences of Teachers in Reshaping their Lives

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Abstract. This study revealed the experiences of junior high school teachers who changed their lives by improving their socio-emotional intelligence. Ten (10) secondary school district of Digos City Division teachers who wanted to improve their socio-emotional intelligence in handling teaching challenges participated in the study. A phenomenological approach was used in this study to extract participant ideas. A virtual in-depth interview was used to learn more about each person's story of improving their socio-emotional intelligence and changing their lives. The thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study revealed the experiences of junior high school teachers as they enhanced their socio-emotional intelligence in reshaping their lives and delved into self-regulation and control over reaction, working hard on conflict resolution and challenges in addressing the learning gaps. The teachers were challenged to deal with the learners' academic performance gaps. However, the teachers employed the following coping mechanisms: enhancing self-awareness, maintaining a positive working environment, and encouraging personal development. The insight drawn from the study's findings was intensifying teacher engagement, developing teachers professionally, and positive student engagement. The teacher needs to be equipped with hard and soft skills to meet the needs of the new century and to face the challenges of the new era boldly. They may have a positive mindset, embrace changes, and explore possibilities by providing children with a safe and positive learning environment.

KEY WORDS

1. socio-emotional intelligence 2. enhancement 3. reshaping lives

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1. Introduction

Teaching is intrinsically an emotional practice, given the centrality of emotions in the teaching and learning process. Therefore, teachers in the twenty-first century increasingly have to have skills in responding to classroom emotional situations. Therefore, the way teachers shape and handle their emotional states and those of their learners is central to educational success. Teachers' emotional intelligence skills are a success indicator for a healthy pedagogical relationship in a global sense. Enhancing socio-emotional intelligence poses significant challenges for teachers striving to improve both their professional practices and personal lives. One major obstacle is teachers' limited time due to their many responsibilities, such as lesson planning, grading, and administrative tasks. This leaves little room for teachers to self-reflect and develop emotional intelligence skills. Additionally, access to comprehensive training and

resources focused on socio-emotional learning is often inadequate, hindering educators' ability to acquire essential tools and strategies. Another difficulty lies in the personal growth required to develop socio-emotional intelligence. This process demands that teachers confront their own emotions, biases, and communication styles, which can be uncomfortable and necessitates an ongoing commitment to introspection and improvement. Moreover, socio-emotional intelligence is influenced by cultural and contextual factors, presenting another challenge. Teachers in diverse settings must navigate these differences sensitively to effectively foster empathy and emotional awareness among their students. In Pakistan, given the centrality of emotions to the teaching and learning process, effective teaching practices should be developed, students should be emotionally educated, and they should remain emotionally healthy. Teachers need to learn emotional intelligence. Therefore, experiencing positive emotions may prompt teachers to build positive emotional connections with students, parents, and co-teachers, which allows them to deal effectively with some of the most typical classroom conflicts (Valente et al., 2020). Training in its origin and meaning carries a significant value and message. Therefore, training is arranged to meet the changing demands of the sector. It is a planned, organized, and scheduled activity designed to enhance individual and organizational performance (Tahira et al., 2019). Another cultural aspect influencing the understanding of emotional intelligence (EI) in Nigeria involves the high regard for authority figures, such as teachers. Cultural norms emphasizing deference and respect may inhibit Nigerian students from openly expressing their emotions to their teachers. Consequently, this cultural dynamic might lead to underestimating teachers' emotional intelligence within the Nigerian educational context (Duru, 2021). Additionally, religion plays a significant role in Nigerian culture and could affect how EI is perceived and assessed. Nigeria's religious diversity shapes emotional experiences, as religious beliefs and practices influence emotional regulation and expression. These factors contribute to cultural variations in emotional intelligence among Nigerians (Olaoye, 2020). Malejane and Diraditsile (2019) conducted a study highlighting Botswana's educational policy, noting its inadequate implementation at the primary school level, which serves as the foundation for secondary schooling. Despite students' performance in earlier education stages, they are automatically enrolled in higher learning institutions, often lacking emotional stability. Factors contributing to this instability include socioeconomic backgrounds, poverty, and social challenges. These issues place significant demands on teachers who interact with these students daily, affecting both the classroom environment and academic outcomes. Botha and Hugo (2021) further discuss the global issue of teachers leaving the profession prematurely due to various factors, including the challenges posed by student emotional instability, which can also impact teachers' emotional intelligence (EI). The study explores how emotional intelligence influences teachers' classroom performance in Botswana's Southeast Region primary schools. This research is crucial for education stakeholders seeking to integrate EI into teaching and learning processes, thereby enhancing educational effectiveness in environments where limited research on EI and its impact on teacher performance exists, potentially influencing academic success in developing countries like Botswana. In the Philippines, teachers encountered misbehavior among learners when face-to-face classes started. Learners struggled with how to deal with peers' and teachers' behaviors. Several studies have shown that emotionally intelligent teachers have more skills to manage the various challenges of daily life more effectively, have a strong influence on students, encourage growth, spread a pos-

itive atmosphere in the classroom, and create healthy, stimulating environments for learning (Nadeem, 2023). People express emotions differently based on their upbringing, social interactions, and cultural background. Emotions and their responses can have both beneficial and detrimental effects. Consequently, when teachers face personal challenges, preventing these issues from affecting their teaching performance can be difficult. Strategies such as compartmentalizing problems and utilizing emotional intelligence are essential for managing and preventing adverse impacts in the workplace. In contrast, Filipino teachers may handle such situations differently due to their innate optimism, efficiency, resilience, and hopefulness. It is, therefore, important to explore and understand the strengths of Filipino teachers in these areas. The Philippine Constitution underscores the significance of providing quality education (Article XIV, 1987 Philippine Constitution), which hinges largely on the competence and effectiveness of its educators (Jamian, Ibadallah, Fook, 2019). According to Floreno (2021), many educators in the Digos City Division, especially in the Secondary Schools District, have expressed concern about the frequency of students' misbehavior, which is becoming a significant source of stress for them. Due to the student's disruptive behavior, teachers now have to spend a significant amount of time handling these behavioral problems. The ongoing battle to manage disruptive behavior undermines the capacity to efficiently support the teaching-learning process because classrooms frequently become chaotic, making it difficult for teachers to keep things under control and provide high-quality instruction. This circumstance affects students' academic performance and overall educational ex-

perience in addition to the classroom. Teachers need to build caring and trusting relationships where students feel safe and secure and where learning can thrive. They must have good communication and listening skills, be patient and compassionate, and spend enough time with students to support them according to their needs. In this context, the researcher developed this study (Ransom, 2019). The outcomes of this study extend to multiple beneficiaries within the educational framework of Digos City Division. Department of Education officials, particularly those in the Secondary Schools District, are poised to benefit from potentially enhancing technical assistance programs for adviser-teachers. This could involve equipping educators with effective teaching strategies and creating policies aimed at institutionalizing socio-emotional training. For adviser-teachers themselves, the study's findings offer a reflective journey into their thoughts, past experiences, and the challenges they have faced while enhancing socio-emotional intelligence. Such insights can be a pivotal baseline for their ongoing professional development plans. The study also sheds light on the learning dynamics between students and competent teachers, emphasizing preparation for future responsibilities and fostering positive behavior and responses to various situations. Additionally, it sought to uncover reasons behind varying levels of individuality development among learners. Lastly, future researchers are encouraged to build upon these findings, exploring uncharted aspects of teenage behavior amidst diverse challenges and opportunities. By conducting similar studies in different locations and communities, they could provide richer comparisons and expand the understanding of the phenomena explored.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study aimed to determine teachers' experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights into reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement. One of the best ways to use social awareness with our students was to get to know them and their families. It helps you decide how to approach lessons, present

content, react to student behavior, and more. It also allows you to create opportunities for students to bring their whole selves into your classroom. this study can help formulate interventions or enhancement programs that specifically support or help affected individuals.

1.2. Research Questions—

- (1) What are teachers’ lived experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement?
- (2) What are the teachers’ coping mechanisms for their challenges in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the teachers’ experiences reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement?

*1.3. Definition of Terms—*To make this study more comprehensive, the following terms were operationally defined: Emotional Intelligence was described as the ability to identify, use, understand, and manage emotions healthily and effectively. This ability helps students empathize with others and themselves and deal

with difficult situations without getting frazzled. Developing Social Awareness. Activities encouraging empathy and perspective-taking help students understand and respect others’ emotions and perspectives. Teaching empathy enhances students’ interpersonal relationships and contributes to a positive classroom climate (Raver Knitzer, 2002).

*1.4. Significant of the Study—*This study was significant to principals. In it, principals could reveal their lived experiences in implementing educational policies in the school, especially in this new standard setting. They could also adopt the teachers’ coping practices regarding their challenges. This study was equally significant to the school heads. It was a good reference for them to examine the teachers’ chal-

lenges and how to address them. It was also helpful to policymakers to plan and draft future training and seminars for teachers to adequately address implementation gaps in utilizing teachers’ roles and responsibilities in reshaping their students’ lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement. Finally, it was helpful to fellow researchers who wanted to conduct a similar or comparative study.

*1.5. Theoretical Lens—*Socio-economic intelligence showed that individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds may develop varying levels of emotional intelligence due to the socioeconomic factors shaping their experiences and environments. For example, individuals from lower SES backgrounds may face more stressors and adversity, which can impact the development of emotional regulation skills. Therefore, teachers need to be aware of the diverse emotional needs of students from different socio-economic backgrounds and adapt their teaching approaches accordingly (Chitra, 2020).

Schmalor Heine (2022) The research investigated how educators’ experiences mold their socioeconomic intelligence—that is, their aptitude for comprehending and navigating social and economic structures. It inspected how this intelligence affects teachers’ well-being, decision-making, and career success. The research clarified the intricacies of education in larger socioeconomic contexts by examining how educators apply socioeconomic intelligence. This study was anchored on the concept of Salovey and Mayer, which shows that they have adaptive functions, which means that the intelli-

gence quotient does not encompass the competencies that contribute to intelligent and adaptive behavior and that there are individual differences in the way individuals deal with emotions and organize emotional information. The most common emotional intelligence components across these tests were emotion perception/emotion recognition (the ability to identify and differentiate between emotions in oneself and others), emotion understanding (the ability to comprehend complex emotional states, transitions, and the causes and consequences of emotions), and emotion regulation/management (the ability to manage and respond to emotions in oneself and others effectively). These are the central ability emotional intelligence components across different conceptualizations and taxonomies (Schlegel et al., 2019 Vesely Maillefer et al., 2018). Emotional intelligence is now widely used in organizations and graduate schools, and there is an increase in published research supporting it. Discussion about emotional intelligence, whether based on measures or theory, has given little distinction as to behavioral emotional intelligence such as how emotional intelligence appears in a person's actions. The emergent conflicts about the validity of the different theories or measures of emotional intelligence are a likely limit to predicting managerial and leadership effectiveness, engagement, innovation, and organizational citizenship. By adding a behavioral level, the concept of emotional intelligence could relate to work and life outcomes beyond general mental ability and personality traits, avoiding some of the criticisms while providing a more holistic theory of emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is important because it can help you improve your interpersonal relationships, both personally and professionally. The five components of emotional intelligence at work are self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. As such, emotional intelligence exists within personality as a performance trait or ability, a self-schema self-image and trait, and a set of behaviors (i.e., competencies) (Boyatzis, 2018). In recent years, Emotional Intelligence has become the focus of interest for numerous researchers. IE is understood as the ability to facilitate the recognition and regulation of emotions and the generation of adaptive behaviors. The main theories on EI are based on the trait and ability models, which share several common elements, such as the fact that emotions are considered predictors of positive adaptive behaviors (Cecchini et al., 2018). This concept emerged when social trends neglected emotions, and efforts were increasing for people's self-assessment. Educationists consider emotional intelligence tests important for looking at or predicting people's abilities. So, this field is significant for improving society and knowing the importance of emotions in our daily lives. Advocates of emotional intelligence state that people who know their emotions can spend their lives more easily and happily, and such types of people are happier than others. Emotional intelligence (or emotional quotient or EQ) is the ability to understand, use, and manage your emotions positively to relieve stress, communicate effectively, empathize with others, overcome challenges, and defuse conflict. Emotional intelligence helps you build stronger relationships, succeed at school and work, and achieve your career and personal goals. It can also help you connect with your feelings, turn intention into action, and make informed decisions about what matters most to you (Segal et al., 2024). Mindfulness-based approaches have gained prominence in educational settings as effective strategies for enhancing socio-emotional intelligence. These approaches, rooted in practices like meditation and mindful breathing, aim to cultivate self-awareness, emotional regulation, and empathy among students. According to a study by Jennings and Greenberg (2019), mindfulness interventions in schools not only improve students' attention and self-control but

also foster a positive classroom climate conducive to social-emotional learning. Mindfulness techniques promote emotional resilience and interpersonal skills by encouraging students to pay non-judgmental attention to their thoughts and feelings, ultimately contributing to a more supportive and inclusive learning environment (Jennings Greenberg, 2019). This process promotes a deeper understanding of emotional states, fostering resilience by allowing students to navigate challenges with greater clarity and composure. Furthermore, mindfulness enhances interpersonal skills by encouraging empathetic responses and improving communication within the learning environment. Mindfulness-based approaches are becoming increasingly acknowledged for their ability to develop socio-emotional intelligence, particularly in educational contexts. These methods, including mindfulness meditation and conscious awareness of one's thoughts and feelings, improve general well-being, empathy, and self-control. A thorough meta-analysis by Zenner, Herrnleben-Kurz, and Walach (2018) found that school mindfulness interventions have demonstrated noteworthy advantages in several areas, such as better emotional regulation, lower stress levels, and improved social skills in children. According to the study, students who regularly practice mindfulness can better manage their emotions and foster a supportive learning environment that fosters interpersonal development and learning in the classroom (Zenner et al., 2018). Furthermore, mindfulness enhances interpersonal skills by encouraging empathetic responses and improving communication within the learning environment. These benefits contribute significantly to creating a supportive and inclusive atmosphere in schools, where students feel understood and valued, enriching learning experiences and promoting positive social interactions. It is also important to teach students

social skills such as communication, collaboration, and empathy. These skills are vital not only in the classroom but also in life. We can teach these skills through group work, class discussions, and role-playing. According to Siddique et al. (2020), teaching is a challenging process and a vast concept in the teaching field. Since teaching deals with human interaction, one needs to be emotionally intense to manage the emotions involved in teaching and learning activities effectively. Emotional intelligence (EI) is the ability to recognize one's own and other people's emotions, distinguish between feelings, categorize them accordingly, and use emotional information to influence others' thinking and behavior (Abraham Scaria, 2017). So far, only one EI-related study has been conducted in Botswana (Machera using Both university learners to investigate the need to design and develop an EI curriculum for university learners. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. It shows three interconnected working themes. Teachers' experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers, teachers, and learners to provide the necessary skills and knowledge and focus on engaging in meaningful inquiry about their professional practice, would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals of the learning community. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center of the two circles determines that there was a way of exploring the experiences of coping mechanisms of the teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement, a way of teaching and learning development that is very critical to school success.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the research design utilized in the study, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection, the data analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical considerations. The three most prevalent qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for acquiring a particular type of data. Participant observation was suitable for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups were valuable and practical in eliciting data on a group's cultural norms and generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. According to Qutoshi (2018), phenomenology as a philosophy provides a theoretical guideline for researchers to understand phenomena at the level of subjective reality. This philosophical framework or the theory of subjective reality plays a crucial role in understanding the actor or the subject regarding a particular event or phenomenon relating to their life. The researcher adopted interviews, observations, and discussions as data collection strategies within a phenomenological method of inquiry; therefore, phenomenology has both philosophical and methodological stances. To this end, one needs to understand it from a historical and philosophical standpoint. It implies that phenomenology was an approach to educate our vision, define our position, broaden how we see the world around us, and study the lived experience at a deeper level. It, therefore, holds both the characteristics of philosophy and a method of inquiry. This paper sought phenomenological answers to some of the critical questions about phenomenology as a philosophy, a human science, and a method of inquiry that it claims. The questions it may answer are: What is phenomenology? How do philosophical underpinnings support the method of inquiry to understand the lived

world at a conscious level? How do we conduct phenomenological research? What are the methodological tools that help to understand this human science? Why is the phenomenological approach critical? (Qutoshi, 2018).

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated on below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. A research paradigm was a set of accepted ideas and viewpoints among scientists regarding how issues can be recognized and handled (Perera, 2018). A research paradigm is a fundamental and comprehensive belief system used to view research phenomena. The researcher's worldview perspective, thinking, school of thought, or set of shared beliefs inform the meaning or interpretation of research data. In research, the researcher must be aware and informed about his/her position on seeing and observing the world and its phenomena. It means he/she needs to have clear philosophical perspectives about how the reality or truth is viewed, how the knowledge was gained by what methods and methodology, and how values are addressed based on a particular research paradigm. Thus, such perspectives and assumptions through which reality, knowledge, methodological approaches, and values were defined under each paradigm were components of the research paradigm (Khatri, 2020). Ontology. Ontology was the philosophical standpoint about the nature of existence or reality, being or becoming, and the basic categories of things that exist and their relations. It examines the researcher's underlying belief system about the nature of being and existence. It helps to conceptualize the form and nature of reality and what you believe could be known about that reality. In the course of research, ontology makes the researcher seek the answer to questions such as: Is there reality in the social world, or is it a construction created by one's mind? What is the nature of reality? In other words, Is the reality of an objective nature or the result of individual cognition? What is the nature of the situation being studied? (Khatri, 2020). Epistemology. The term originated in the mid-19th century from two Greek words: episteme and logos (Steup Neta, 2020). Episteme can be translated as "knowledge," while logos can be translated as "the study of" (Couper, 2020, p. 275). In general terms, epistemology is a branch of philosophy that deals with the theory of knowledge. In a more precise way, the Oxford English Dictionary defines epistemology as "the theory of knowledge and understanding, especially about its methods, validity, and scope, and the distinction between justified belief and opinion." I will identify phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." It is concerned with the very bases of knowledge – its nature and forms, how it can be acquired, and how it can be communicated to other human beings. It focuses on the nature of human knowledge and comprehension that you, as the researcher or knower, can acquire to extend, broaden, and deepen understanding in your field of research (Khatri, 2020). The purpose of this research was to gather essential details on the teachers' experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement in the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division. I assured that I would establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the teachers' experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhance-

ment. Axiology is another component of the research paradigm that deals with ethical issues that need to be considered during research work (Khatri 2020). It involves defining, evaluating, and understanding concepts of right and wrong behavior related to the research. It considers what value we shall attribute to the different aspects of our research, the participants, the data, and the audience to which we shall report the results of our research. I uphold the dignity and value of every piece of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants' answers and carefully interpret them in light of the participants' interpretations. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption emphasized that I may write in a literary, informal style using my personal voice and qualitative terminologies and limited definitions. In the context of the study, I used the first person to explain the teachers' experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement and thoroughly discussed their responses during the

interview. This concept emerged when social trends neglected the emotions, and efforts were on the rise for the people's self-assessment. Educationists take emotional intelligence tests as essential for looking at or predicting the abilities of people. So, this field is significant for the improvement of society for knowing the importance of emotions in our daily lives. Advocates of emotional intelligence state that people who know their emotions can spend their life more easily and happily, and such types of people are happier than other people. According to Varpio (2018), in the *Writer's Craft* section, we offer simple tips to improve your writing in one of three areas: Energy, Clarity, and Persuasiveness. Each entry focuses on a key writing feature or strategy, illustrates how it commonly goes wrong, teaches the grammatical underpinnings necessary to understand it, and offers suggestions to wield it effectively. This implies that we must be convincing in writing our research findings. We have to persuade readers to agree with our results and the inferences we make from them (Varpio, 2018).

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology is distinct from the method. A method is simply the tool used to answer your research questions — how, in short, you would collect your data. At the same time, methodology is the rationale for the research approach, and the lens through which the analysis occurs (Brookshier, 2018). In this study, teachers' challenges and coping mechanisms were unleashed from their narratives, specifically those teachers from the Secondary Schools District, Digos City Division. Research on phenomenology attempts to understand the nature of things by using people's experiences as a guide. Translated, it means "study of phenomena." Putting it in another manner, it is examining the significance of these objects or phenomena in the

eyes of the individuals you are researching (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023). Studying a person's lived experience of a phenomenon in a way that brings out its fundamental elements is the challenging aspect of the research. (Neubauer et al., 2019) that is considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena". From the definition, human experience is viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. Phenomenology as a philosophy and a method of inquiry is not limited to an approach to knowing, it is rather an intellectual engagement in interpretations and meaning-making that is used to understand the lived world of human beings at a

conscious level (Qutoshi, 2018). Moreover, the outcomes of a phenomenological study broaden the mind, improve the ways of thinking to see

a phenomenon, and enable one to see ahead and define researchers' posture through the intentional study of lived experiences.

2.3. Design and Procedure—The method I used is qualitative research with a phenomenological approach. Phenomenology is defined as the “study of the meaning of phenomena or the study of the particular” (Tenny et al., 2022). The main aim of phenomenology is to capture, as closely as possible, the way a phenomenon was lived by people who participated in the phenomenon (Creswell Poth, 2018). Most often, phenomenology is used for studies that are focused on understanding the essence of

a particular group of people's lived experiences (Creswell Poth, 2018). I used the phenomenological inquiry method and focused on subjective understanding and biases to look at what the participants said (Juma, 2023). The interviews were conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of a certain event, circumstance, or experience. Through this process, I constructed the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon.

2.4. Research Participants—The research study comprised ten (10) informants as participants. The chosen informants were junior high school teachers coming from the Secondary School District, Digos City Division. All the participants were public school teachers from nearby. They had to have been teachers for a minimum of three years. All of the participants, irrespective of their age, sex, or marital status, were from junior high schools. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. According to Young Casey (2018), decisions regarding anticipated

sample sizes are often taken by qualitative researchers prior to data collection. Estimates are typically required for resource planning, grant applications, and human subjects review committees. Researchers have to determine whether the sample has been sufficiently resilient to address the research objectives once a study was ongoing or finished. The difficulty lies in selecting a sample that would yield comprehensive and significant results with the least amount of needless strain on participants and the use of limited resources, such as time and money for the study.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the communication between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Thus, it was imperative that particular ethical norms be developed in this regard. The connection and understanding that is established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of different ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, the

establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Perspectives on subject protection and carrying out research in accordance with moral principles are examples of ethical elements (Pietila et al., 2019). The protection of human subjects through the application of appropriate ethical principles is important in all research studies. In a qualitative study, ethical considerations have a particular resonance due to the in-depth nature of the study process. The existing ethical guidance for undertaking qualitative research often provides

general guidelines rather than focusing on how to apply them in practice, particularly when interviewing a vulnerable group of women (Mohd Arifin, 2018). The process of obtaining Consent consists of the following: consent should be given freely (voluntary), subjects should understand what is being asked of them, and involved persons must be competent to consent. This means, that to participate in a research study, participants need to be adequately informed about the research, comprehend the information, and have the power of freedom of choice to allow them to decide whether to participate or decline. Participant's agreement to participate in this study was obtained only after a thorough explanation of the research process. All participants were required to provide written informed consent. The potential participants were approached individually and given an explanation of the purpose of the study and data collection process. They were given an appropriate time to ask questions and address any concerns. It was explained that as their participation was voluntary, refusing to participate or withdraw from the study while it was in progress would not affect them. A participant's information sheet was provided to further explain the study. The poten-

tial participants were given appropriate time (in this case: 24 hours up to one week) to read the information sheet and to decide whether or not they wanted to be involved in this study. They were required to sign the informed consent form before the interview to indicate their permission to be part of the study and this signature was confirmed before the interview session. An explanation was given to potential participants that they had a right to withdraw from the study at any time even after the informed consent had been signed. Consent to record the interview was also asked from them (Arifin, 2018). In this study, I followed ethical considerations as part of the process of qualitative research. It was my responsibility to completely inform the participants about the different aspects of the research in incomprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: the nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results were published and used. In the same manner, this study was submitted to the ethics committee of the Rizal Memorial College graduate school for verification and approval.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—In this study, my job was to try to comprehend the participants' thoughts and emotions. It entails getting informants to speak about topics that can be quite private to them. At times, the participant finds it easy to recollect prior experiences, while at other times, the experiences under discus-

sion are still relatively recent in their memories. Nonetheless, my main duty is to protect participants and their data while the data are being gathered. Before the study begins, procedures for this kind of safeguarding have to be made clear to the participants and authorized by the appropriate research ethical review board.

2.7. Data Collection—Selecting participants or locations for the study, obtaining access to them, and establishing a connection with them are crucial steps in the process that ensure high-quality data from them. One of the process's closely connected steps was coming up

with a plan for the deliberate sampling of people or locations. The appropriate data-gathering methods must be decided upon when the researcher selects the participants or locations. For gathering this data, the researcher creates documented methods or protocols for data col-

lection, such as observational or interview methods. I also need to anticipate possible "field problems" that might come up while gathering data. These problems include insufficient information, having to depart the area or field early, or adding to the loss of knowledge. Thus, cleaning and organizing the data collected is a necessary and crucial step because it will increase the correctness of your data and facilitate evaluation, according to Paredes (2024). In this study, there are seven steps in the process of data collection. First is the site or individual; the participants were the teachers from the Secondary Schools district, Digos City Division. Second was the access and rapport. On October 18, 2023, a letter from the Dean of the Graduate School was given to the graduate student for the approval of the Division Superintendent; on October 25, 2023, a letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal, and the concerned junior high school teachers was prepared for easy data collection. The third was the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phe-

nomenon being studied. There were ten (10) informants selected in this study. The selected teachers were considered a group of individuals who could best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data on November 15, 2023. The fourth is the forms of data; the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the ten (10) informants on November 20-30, 2023. The fifth was the recording procedures. A protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form records information collected during an observation or interview. The recording and data collection took place December 10-15, 2023. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or seventh step was storing data on December 20, 2023; Davidson (1996) suggested using the database to back up information collected and note changes for all types of research studies.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, all collected data were cautiously inspected and thoughtfully evaluated. Initially, the researcher discussed their own experiences with the subject they were studying. The researcher then proceeded by describing in detail the phenomenon as it had personally affected them. For the researcher to focus on the participants, this is an attempt to put their personal experiences aside. The researcher generated a list of significant claims. Statements that describe the person's experience with the topic at hand followed, allocated the same importance to these important claims, and begin compiling a list of distinct, non-overlapping statements. After selecting the important assertions, the researcher organized them into "meaning units," or themes, which are more comprehensive informational units. They

penned an account of "what" the phenomenon's study participants experienced. The researcher then went on to provide an account of "how" the event transpired. In what has been referred to as a "structural description". The researcher considered the environment and circumstances around the phenomena. At last, the creation of an overview of the phenomenon that incorporated the structural and textural explanations followed. The "essence" of the interaction is this passage, which also serves as a phenomenological study's conclusion. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis is the flexible method that can be both for explorative studies, where the researcher does not have a clear idea of what patterns are being searched for, as

well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher knows exactly what he or she is interested in. No matter which type of study is being done and for what purpose, the most important thing in the analysis is the respect the data and try to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Triangulation of Data. According to Noble and Heale (2019), research triangulation refers to the process that helps to increase the credibility and validity of research. In other words, research triangulation aims at validating the results of a study. Triangulation, sometimes, makes use of mixed methods to achieve the aim of validating research findings. However, triangulation was not the same as mixed methods. Mixed methods combine quantitative and qualitative research approaches to getting research questions answered; while triangulation describes how the researcher makes use of all the multiple approaches in the study to extract the required

information as well as critically analyze findings (Social Sciences Research Laboratories, 2018); thus establishing validity and credibility. Environmental triangulation. The use of Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where the findings can be influenced by certain environmental factors. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as the time, day, and season in which the study took place. The idea is to determine which of these factors influence the information received, these factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, the validity can be established (Naeem, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement as mentioned is the use of environmental triangulation best suits the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—The analytical framework of the study was based on Colaizzi's seven-step descriptive phenomenological data analysis method which has been demonstrated to be rigorous and robust. Colaizzi's seven-step analysis method provides researchers with clear, logical, and systematic steps (Wirihana et al., 2018; Kwang-Ok et al., 2018). I observed several steps in conducting a thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. Following Colaizzi's analysis method, I relied on my resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. The researcher used several nights to listen to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing to con-

ventions with transcribers. Some negotiated to layout and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step was data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. The researcher selected quotations about central issues, or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used several different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was very

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

useful in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the data analysis method outlined by Colaizzi's descriptive phenomenological consisted of seven (7) steps used in analyzing the data. Step 1. Read and re-read all the transcribed interviews in order to make sense of them; Step 2. Extract significant statements. These are phrases or sentences that directly pertain to the investigated phenomenon; Step 3. The process of giving meaning to the statements. During

the process, pertinent quotes are broadly categorized, subsequently, themes are generated based on multiple statements that convey similar meanings; Step 4. Repeat steps 1-3 for each interview then the researcher can begin to create themes based on the formulated meanings; Step 5. Compile an exhaustive description of everything generated in steps 1-4. Step 6. Summarize the exhaustive description so that there is an identification of the fundamental structure of the phenomenon; Step 7. Credibility of the data is ensured through discussions with experts and independent reviewers.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study—*

Trustworthiness is all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In this qualitative study, trustworthiness is very vital because the result and findings of the research study would depend on the process of how it is being conducted by me. When evaluating a research study's significance, trustworthiness is fundamental. Sincerity in all of the data and information is necessary because of the nature of the qualitative research. A trustworthy study is one that you can read, discuss, and take pride in as a researcher. Credibility is the extent to which the qualitative researcher believes the findings of the study to be accurate. Credibility is a subjective measure and it is a perceived quality, that other people determine based on the interaction of numerous factors (Budzowski, 2019). Transferability is how I as the qualitative researcher demonstrate that the research study's findings apply to other contexts. To be able to help the reader determine whether your findings are applicable to their own context, it is your responsibility as a researcher to give a "thick description" of the participants and the research methodology. This is referred to as the "transferability judgment." This suggests that since you are unaware of their specific circumstances, the reader, not you, determines the transferability (Korstjens, 2018). Confirmability is the degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on participants' responses and not any potential bias or personal motivations of the researcher. This involves making sure that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a certain narrative. The information using the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher which highlights every step of data analysis that was made to provide a rationale for the decisions made. Thus, confirmability (objectivity) is the neutrality of the researcher in interpreting findings; findings being free from bias, including social-desirability bias, which can be inherent since researchers design and execute tools. Maintaining reflexivity is key to managing such bias (Nyirenda et al., 2020). Dependability is the extent to which the study could be repeated by other researchers and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use an inquiry audit to establish dependability which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and could be repeated. In this component, the use of the database is very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references. Dependability (also known as consistency) is one of four criteria for rigor and trustworthiness in qualitative research (Janis, 2022).

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter is enwrapped with the results accumulated from the lived experiences of teachers who have reshaped their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement. They engaged in different training and developmental programs to enhance their proficiency in their domains. To better equip our younger generation with up-to-date skills and techniques, we have to focus on including the latest materials in curriculum and teacher training workshops. This chapter further discusses the coping mechanisms of the challenges they encountered while dealing with reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement. This chapter discussed the themes

that emerged from the data gathered. The result primarily presents the description and background of the participants who are assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities. Before the discussion, the researcher would like to establish the symbols used as the researcher presents the quotations based on the responses of the study participants. Regarding the transcriptions of the conducted interviews, the researcher also used codes to refer to the participants of the research.

3.1. The Experiences of Teachers in Reshaping Their Lives through Socio-Emotional Intelligence Enhancement—Training and development is a tool to reshape the lives of teachers not only in content by also in interpersonal relationships with the community, giving them the capacity to increase their efficacy and effectiveness and give them new horizons, resolution, and determination. However, working on classroom emotions has become vital nowadays for students' emotional growth or positive academic achievement. It is hoped that successful teachers have a high level of emotional competencies. Emotional intelligence forecasts positive and successful results in all fields of life, and consequently, it dominates all fields of education. Teachers need to be trained in emotional intelligence to manage their own emotions to help students. This makes emotional

intelligence important for both teachers and students. Obviously, due to the demands of their work, teachers need to be aware of their abilities, responsibilities, and role in the academic field. To detect weaknesses in their abilities, teachers necessarily need to seek the opinion of experts and leaders in the field. To manage the socio-emotional development of students effectively, teachers, too, need socio-emotional competency. To deal with student's behavior problems like bullying, aggression, and non-response in the classroom, teachers need skills related to socio-emotional competencies. The ten (10) secondary school teachers with varying backgrounds from the Secondary Schools District opined. In conclusion, most teachers struggled and adjust to their personal and professional lives after the disasters and calamities experienced.

3.1.1. Positive Effects: Greater empathy and understanding—Understanding students' deeper emotions and experiences represents a significant change in how teachers perceive their role. It extends beyond grasping academic challenges or behaviors; it entails forming connections with students' emotions, motivations, and obstacles at a profound level. This empathy enables educators to look past superficial observations and identify the underlying factors that impact students' conduct and academic achievements. Establishing a trusting relationship through empathy is essential. Participants emphasized prioritizing empathy and understanding in their role as educators represents a commitment to more than just academic proficiency. It reflects a deeper understanding of the

holistic needs of my students—their emotional well-being, motivations, and challenges. Creating a culture of empathy and understanding as a teacher not only enhances personal well-being and professional growth but also enriches the educational experience for everyone involved. It fosters a community where empathy is valued as a core principle, leading to a more compassionate and resilient learning environment where everyone can thrive. The responses of the participants verify the perspectives of Mikkoen (2020) that teachers with more empathy and understanding are better able to address behavioral issues with compassion and patience. Instead of reacting rashly to disruptive behavior, they view discipline as an opportunity to teach emotional regulation and conflict resolution skills.

This proactive approach reduces punitive measures while creating a positive classroom environment in which students feel safe to express themselves authentically. Furthermore, empathetic responses to challenges foster a nurturing environment in which mistakes are viewed as opportunities for growth rather than punishment. Teachers frequently describe a profound shift in empathy and understanding as they work to improve their socio-emotional intelligence. This transformation begins with a greater understanding of their own emotions and how they influence their interactions with students (Dolev Leshem, 2018). Teachers become more aware of their own emotions, which leads to a greater sensitivity to their students' emotional cues and needs. This self-awareness enables them to approach teaching as a holistic endeavor that takes into account each student's emotional well-being, rather than simply a transfer of knowledge. Empathy, a key component of socio-emotional intelligence, develops as teachers learn to see the world through their students' eyes. Educators gain insight into the daily challenges and triumphs that their

students face by actively listening and observing them. This understanding extends beyond academic performance to include the socioeconomic, cultural, and personal backgrounds that influence each student's journey. Empathetic engagement allows teachers to create a supportive environment in which students feel understood and valued, fostering a sense of belonging that is essential for academic success (Akamatsu Ghergel, 2021). Teachers who have improved their socio-emotional intelligence are more likely to adapt their teaching methods to meet their students' different needs (Devis-Roziental Farquharson, 2020). They understand that empathy entails not only understanding emotions but also effectively responding to them. This could include implementing personalized emotional regulation strategies or offering additional support to students experiencing personal difficulties. Teachers model compassionate behavior by demonstrating empathy in their interactions, which encourages students to develop their socioemotional skills and cultivate empathy for their peers.

3.1.2. Improved classroom management— Participants foresee that future classroom management will increasingly highlight the significance of cultivating robust relationships with students, nurturing a positive classroom atmosphere, and incorporating technology to enrich engagement and communication. As we endeavor to accommodate students' diverse needs and promote inclusive learning environments, personalized methods for supporting behavior and fostering social-emotional learning will gain prominence. Establishing clear expectations and behavior norms at the outset of the school year is more than just a procedural step—it's a foundational strategy for fostering a positive classroom environment. When teachers collaborate with students to set these expectations, it promotes a sense of ownership

and accountability among the students. This collaborative process helps students understand what is expected of them in terms of behavior, participation, and respect for others. These findings align with Prinsoo (2021) that one important aspect of better classroom management is the ability to remain calm and composed in stressful situations. Teachers with higher socio-emotional intelligence can better control their emotions, preventing conflicts from escalating. This composure allows them to respond to disruptive behaviors with patience and empathy rather than frustration. Teachers set the tone in the classroom by modeling calmness and encouraging students to emulate these behaviors. Over time, this results in a more respectful and controlled learning environment. Takacs (2020) stated that teachers with higher socio-emotional

intelligence report stronger relationships with their students, which is critical for effective classroom management. When students feel understood and valued, they are more likely to follow classroom rules and participate constructively. These teachers use empathy to develop trust and rapport with their students, fostering a sense of community in the classroom. This sense of belonging reduces disruptive behavior because students are more invested in maintaining a peaceful classroom environment. As a result, teachers devote more time to facilitating learning rather than conflict resolution. Another

3.1.3. Enhanced conflict resolution skills.—Enhanced conflict resolution skills encompass the capability to manage and resolve conflicts effectively across different environments like classrooms, workplaces, or communities. These skills include methods such as constructive communication, empathy, active listening, negotiation, and problem-solving. Developing these abilities enables individuals to navigate conflicts peacefully, foster positive relationships, and establish harmonious environments that encourage productivity, collaboration, and mutual comprehension. Such skills are essential for cultivating a supportive and inclusive atmosphere where differences are approached respectfully and solutions are achieved through collaborative efforts. One of the most important aspects of developing conflict resolution skills is the ability to remain calm and composed during a dispute. Teachers with higher socio-emotional intelligence can better control their own emotions, which is critical in heated situations (Board, 2022). This emotional regulation enables them to handle conflicts with patience and empathy rather than frustration or anger. Teachers model calm and empathetic behavior for students to emulate, which aids in the de-escalation of tense situations. Over time, this results in a more respectful and peaceful classroom environment.

advantage of developing socio-emotional intelligence is the ability to implement proactive management strategies. Teachers learn to recognize early signs of distress or potential conflicts and intervene before they escalate (Tiwari, 2023). They use techniques like restorative practices and social-emotional learning activities to anticipate and meet the needs of their students. This proactive approach reduces disruptions while promoting a positive classroom culture. Students learn to manage their emotions and interactions better, resulting in a more efficient and focused educational experience.

Teachers with strong conflict-resolution skills also emphasize the importance of active listening in resolving disputes. They learn to listen to all parties involved in a conflict as part of socio-emotional intelligence training, ensuring that each student's point of view is heard and valued. This inclusive approach makes students feel understood and respected, which is frequently the first step toward resolving a disagreement. Teachers can foster trust and facilitate effective problem-solving by validating students' emotions and experiences. This approach not only resolves the immediate conflict but also teaches students important communication and negotiation skills. Reflecting on their experiences, teachers frequently express renewed confidence and satisfaction in their ability to manage classroom conflicts. They recognize the positive impact of their increased socio-emotional intelligence on their students' behavior and well-being (Marks, 2024). Furthermore, having effective conflict resolution skills helps teachers experience less stress and burnout. The ability to handle disputes calmly and constructively benefits not only the classroom environment but also the teacher's professional and personal well-being (Cambi, 2019). Finally, improving socio-emotional intelligence leads to a more rewarding and sustainable teaching career.

3.1.4. *Challenges Encountered: Self-regulation and control over reaction—*

The majority of them believed that through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement, they were sure that their learners were comfortable with them because learners felt comfortable asking questions during classes. They felt positive and happy about this reality experience. This entails identifying and appreciating the full range of emotions felt, from joy and contentment to rage and grief. Moreso, the respondents were aware of this which allows for better self-regulation and control over reactions in various situations. Teachers experienced altering their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement including increased self-awareness, improved interpersonal interactions, professional growth, leadership development, personal well-being, and work-life balance. These transforming stories highlight the significant impact of socio-emotional intelligence on the lives of educators. The responses highlight how crucial socioemotional intelligence is for educators to change both their personal and professional lives. They place a strong emphasis on establishing welcoming learning environments for students, developing self-awareness to effectively control emotions, and highlighting the benefits for wellbeing, career advancement, and interpersonal relationships. Overall, better teaching practices and student outcomes result from placing a higher priority on socio-emotional intelligence. Since motivation and emotion are essential elements of self-regulation, identical guidelines apply to interventions aimed at enhancing teachers' self-regulation. Treatments designed to modify self-regulation abilities, such as the training developed by (Kramarski Heaysman, 2021) to help teachers become better self-regulators, can also have an impact on teachers' motivation and emotional state. As a result, we must be conscious of how the three constructs intersect. Since effects may occur in all three domains as opposed to only the intervention's target domain, this knowledge is crucial when developing interventions. Demands from educators, parents, students, and business leaders, along with thorough research demonstrating wide-ranging, beneficial effects for both kids and adults, have made social and emotional learning (SEL) an increasingly important component of education (Mahoney et al., 2021). Therefore, social, and emotional teachers set the tempo of the classroom. It improves certain traits of the personality and behaviors of the student by inculcating civic and empathetic sense in them. Teachers' socio-emotional enhancement was able to help in dealing with teens. This development showed positive results in that they were able to control their emotions and minimized overreactions to situations. Motivational variables have been identified as key factors for academic success and cover aspects such as intrinsic task interest and value, self-efficacy, self-concept, goal orientation, self-attributions, and the regulation of one's motivation (Eccles Wigfield, 2020; Hattie et al., 2020; Schunk and DiBenedetto, 2020). Teachers with higher self-concept, self-efficacy, or task value are often more advanced at difficult tasks, show deeper learning approaches, become more interested and deeply engrossed in activities, set more challenging goals, and maintain a stronger commitment to those goals compared to those with lower self-efficacy (Karlen et al., 2019). The quality of teacher motivation should also make a critical difference in student outcomes, such as extrinsic motivation to fulfill one's duties in order to earn a salary versus intrinsic motivation to promote students' growth. As pointed out by (Bardach and Klassen, 2021), different motivational orientations are likely to promote different instructional strategies, thus affecting students in different ways. Thus, teacher emotions can also exert strong effects on student outcomes, including students' own emotions (Frenzel et al., 2018; Goetz et al., 2021), their well-being, and their achievement. Viewing from another perspective, it seems plausible to presume teachers who

lack self-regulatory skills will find it difficult or even impossible to construct the self-regulation of their students.

3.1.5. Working hard on conflict resolution—Teachers struggled to alter their lives through socio-emotional intelligence upgrading to provide useful insights for educational administration. Prioritizing the development of teachers' socio-emotional intelligence improves not only individual educators but also has far-reaching implications for overall educational quality and student well-being. Most of the respondents narrated that personal well-being, improved classroom dynamics, professional growth, leadership, resilience, and flexibility are all examples of teachers' lived experiences in transforming their lives. The aforementioned statements underscore the noteworthy consequences of augmenting the socio-emotional intelligence of educators, on both the teaching profession as a whole and individual teachers. Benefits like better classroom dynamics, professional development, leadership abilities, resilience, and flexibility are highlighted. They also stress the significance of professionalism in resolving disputes, refraining from rumors, and encouraging flexible behavior. Overall, putting a high priority on socio-emotional intelligence improves relationships, self-awareness, stress management, and teaching strategies, all of which improve the quality of education and the well-being of students (Groneberg, 2019). Research showed the effectiveness of positive action in the development of teachers' emotional skills, increasingly recognizing teachers being emotionally intelligent as the basis for a good relationship with students, for providing a steady and wholesome classroom environment (Maamari Majdalani, 2019). Other research confirmed that school teachers' EI is a stress and burnout protection factor (Schoeps et al., 2019), associated with higher professional performance, lower feelings of tiredness, helpful for the teaching-learning process, related to the promotion of an appropriate emotional climate and also to effective classroom management (Valente, 2019). According to Lalegani et al. (2019), in an educational institution, conflict resolution is the leader's responsibility. An educator must be ready to deal with conflicts. To prevent or limit conflict, leadership should seek the proper and impartial implementation of a professional code of conduct, ground rules, and discipline. Leadership is a process by which one person or a group sets the purpose or direction for others and helps them achieve goals (Piryani Piryani, 2019). Providing conflict management skills could help raise the emotional intelligence of future managers. As proposed by Kim Plester, (2018), providing conflict management skills could help raise the emotional intelligence of future managers. As a result, it is the responsibility of aspiring teachers to be equipped with various life skills and to have an impact on one another. Without a doubt, the majority of teacher trainees have adequate knowledge and professional growth as a result of their teacher training program. This concept emerged when social trends neglected the emotions and efforts were on the rise for the people's self-assessment. Educationists take emotional intelligence tests as important for looking at or predicting the abilities of people. So, this field is very important for the improvement of society for knowing the importance of emotions in our daily lives. Emotionally intelligent teachers show care for students, create an emotional climate in the classroom that develops the student learning environment, and help the teachers to become more effective in ensuring academic achievement. Emotionally intelligent teachers represent an important context for the development of positive classroom

relationships. Although there are many studies on the benefits of teacher EI in the classroom (Schoeps et al., 2019), there is a shortage of investigations that study how teachers' emotional intelligence influences classroom conflict management. Research confirmed that teachers with more EI present greater integration and

more cohesive levels of commitment for conflict resolution with students in the classroom. They apply more integrating and compromising strategies for conflict management and less strategy of avoiding, dominating, and obliging (Valente Lourenco, 2022).

3.1.6. Challenges in addressing the learning gaps—The challenge aside from the behavior of learners is the learning gap due to the distance learning previously implemented to keep school children safe. Teachers agreed that the modular modality caused a gap in the literacy and numeracy skills of learners. Many learners struggled with reading comprehension. The participants of the study claimed that they were challenged with how to deal with the gaps that are evident in the learners' academic performance. The responses of the participants verify the perspectives of Heather (2020); the first step in addressing learning gaps is to identify exactly where and what those gaps are and which learners struggle with them. The author noted that quizzes are a quick and easy way to formatively assess learners on what they have learned. She added that these can be mini end-of-topic quizzes or even one covering a few units of a subject. Teachers must ensure a good spread and mix of questions to uncover learning gaps. After knowing the gaps, teachers must apply the necessary actions and test again the mastery level acquired by the learners through quizzes. The perennial demand for education and training in the face of limited education infrastructure to accommodate the surge in pop-

ulation expulsion, coupled with the growing number of individuals seeking more knowledge and credentials, has led to the establishment of distance education centers throughout the world (Gregori, Zhang, Galván-Fernández Fernández-Navarro, 2018). This has led to the challenge of gaps in the students' learning. Through these steps, learning gaps can be addressed and bridged. Moreover, in the model of Cabigao (2020) on effective teaching learning in the pandemic period, aside from teachers' and parents' roles, technology likewise dictates its success. Providing technology support and provision to our learners is a great challenge to education officials and advocates in truly addressing the existing learning gaps for the holistic development of every learner today and beyond. Figure 3 shows the teachers' Experiences in Reshaping Their Lives Through Socio-Emotional Intelligence Enhancement and the emergence of the two themes with their sub-themes: Challenges Encountered with Self-Regulation and Control Over Reaction, Working Hard on Conflict Resolution, and Challenges in Addressing the Learning Gaps and excessive administrative tasks and Positive Effects with subthemes namely; Greater Empathy and Understanding, Improved Classroom Management and Enhanced Conflict Resolution Skills.

3.2. Coping mechanisms of the challenges encountered by the teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement—Social-emotional enhancement in

the context of teaching. The teachers experience challenges considering that negative emotions of teachers have a substantial effect on learning. They succeed in overcoming their difficulties

Fig. 3. The emerging themes of the experiences of teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement

and providing a positive emotional environment. In the study, the challenges were establishing self-awareness, working hard on conflict resolution, and addressing the learning gaps. However, most of the participants in this in-depth inter-

3.2.1. Enhancing self-awareness—The teacher-respondents overcome the challenges they encountered through self-management, which they practiced effectively. They applied techniques like deep breathing, meditation, or taking a break when needed. They revealed that they used several techniques to overcome problems and transform their professional lives. Individuals can traverse hurdles while encouraging personal growth and emotional intelligence by building self-awareness. They narrated that these coping skills to manage stress included creating resilience and cultivating self-awareness to improve their socio-emotional intelligence effectively. The participants underscored the significance of coping strategies in managing obstacles and augmenting socio-emotional aptitude. Self-management practices like deep breathing and meditation, developing self-awareness, and using coping mechanisms like emotional control, mindfulness, and support-seeking are emphasized as the keys to changing lives. These realizations highlight the role that self-awareness and coping mechanisms play in promoting personal development and socio-emotional health. Having self-awareness of one's mood and thoughts related to it is a common definition of self-awareness. It is important for educators to be aware of their ideas and feelings and to know how they may affect how they behave in the classroom. A future teacher needs to be able to regulate and recognize emotions. This is essential because two key goals determine whether communication is successful or unsuccessful: building students' emotional intelligence and developing personal skills that serve as the foundation for

view were not bothered about these challenges and difficulties. Here are some of their strategies or mechanisms to remain professionally effective in teaching while reshaping their lives.

emotional intelligence. A prospective educator ought to be actively engaged in exploring novel methodologies and resources for comprehending and managing emotions, in addition to cultivating empathy (Safina et al., 2020). Teachers who lack emotional intelligence frequently find themselves in a bind and leave the classroom feeling agitated, irritated, nervous, and worn out. The dynamics between students and teachers, as well as the classroom atmosphere, can be negatively impacted by a burnt-out teacher. To preserve one's internal balance in the face of all these events, awareness and emotional expression are necessary. Considering all of the conflicts that are common at this point in development, it is also necessary to be able to demonstrate empathy and social sensitivity, especially toward adolescents (Kavita Hassan, 2018). For all of these reasons, the study of teachers' socioemotional competency is crucial in the field of education. You must, therefore, develop coping mechanisms for using self-awareness as a tool to manage stress and burnout if you want to succeed and survive in a classroom. The need to respond to student needs and manage educational institutions forced teachers to overcome their fear of change, adapt to uncertainty, manage frustration, and develop a greater tolerance for individual differences, all of which fall under emotional management (Garcia, 2020). Maintaining equilibrium among significant changes in education, healthcare, living circumstances, and education necessitates socio-emotional competency, self-control, stress prevention, empathy, flexibility, and problem-solving abilities. In the same way, teacher efficacy is influenced by the fact that

teachers need to feel confident in their abilities and have a favorable opinion of their technological pedagogical capabilities (Hadar et al., 2021; Zaragoza et al., 2021; Collado et al., 2020).

3.2.2. Maintaining a positive working environment—Most of the respondents agreed that to maintain a positive working environment is to avoid confrontations. Teachers need to be professional in dealing with conflicts inside the school. They also revealed that avoiding workplace gossip and venting sessions, and practicing adaptive behaviors and thinking spare them from problems and negativity in schools. The teacher-respondents narrated that they spend time with their workmates and family, and avoiding toxic people are their best ways to maintain a positive working environment. They practiced essential skills such as mindfulness, emotional regulation, empathy, conflict resolution, time management, cooperation, leadership, and self-care. They were able to restructure their life and become more effective teachers, leaders, and change agents in their schools. Supporting this observation, Bayounes (2022) has noted that maintaining motivation for study demands determination and optimistic views in work. Creating a positive work environment is essential for empowering teachers to enhance their lives through developing socio-emotional intelligence. When teachers work in a supportive atmosphere, they can improve skills like self-awareness, empathy, and effective communication—critical aspects of socio-emotional intelligence. These skills not only enhance their professional interactions but also contribute to

3.2.3. Encouraging personal development—The teacher-participants narrated that they use numerous coping techniques such as building self-awareness, controlling emotions, finding social support, developing problem-solving abilities, practicing positive self-talk, and adopting a healthy lifestyle. They believed that taking

healthier personal relationships and emotional well-being. Schools that prioritize emotional intelligence help teachers thrive in their personal and professional lives, leading to a more enriching educational experience for students. However, the role of the teacher is to motivate pupils to take an interest in their studies. As a result, to actively serve as a motivator, a teacher must acquire a variety of traits (Moskowitz, 2021). Outside of teaching duties, developing socio-emotional intelligence helps teachers manage their personal lives better, enhancing relationships and well-being. Schools that foster a positive work environment centered on emotional intelligence not only support teachers' professional growth but also foster a cohesive and supportive educational community. For that, teachers must get a great deal of knowledge and keep learning through a variety of media and sources relevant to their professions (Moskowitz, 2021). Schools flourish when teachers feel supported and empowered. Prioritizing the development of socio-emotional intelligence (SEI) enables educators to cultivate self-awareness, which helps them identify and manage stress adeptly. This contributes to a positive mindset and enhances resilience when dealing with obstacles. Furthermore, improved social skills facilitate better communication and collaboration among peers, fostering a cohesive and encouraging environment.

good care of their well-being is equally crucial as personal development. Furthermore, they claimed that efficient coping techniques can assist in overcoming problems and transforming one's life and that individuals can create resilience, flexibility, and emotional well-being by honing coping skills as they navigate personal

growth and development. According to the study of Puertas et al., (2019), teachers ought to concentrate on developing their emotional intelligence (EI) since it helps them better control their emotions, which improves their ability to make decisions in everyday situations in the classroom and is essential to the effectiveness of education. Since this prevents the feeling of dissatisfaction before their professional awareness, which leads to enhanced teaching practice, health, and mental well-being of teachers, positive reinforcement of emotional intelligence (EI) lowers the levels of stress and anxiety that significantly concern society. Throughout their professional lives, teachers must develop a wide range of competencies and skills, which significantly impact their performance. In order to ensure that every student has the opportunity to reach their full potential, educators also adjust to the constant changes that contemporary society faces. Similarly, constant interaction with students, parents, guardians, or peers creates a build-up of stress and strain that frequently results in Burnout Syndrome (BS) (Puertas et al., 2019). The truth is that IE in educators lowers stress and emotional exhaustion and is linked to higher levels of job satisfaction as well as better interpersonal interactions with the overall

school setting. Consequently, it is important to note that resilience has started to become more and more significant in the fields of psychology, sociology, and medicine in recent years. Resilience is an attribute that indicates individuals' psychosocial values and is helpful in the recovery of mental health conditions, as stated by Poloni et al., (2018). It is stated in the study of Puertas et al. (2019) that emotional intelligence is a skill that teachers should acquire, making this essential from subject-specific training since it provides the person the capacity to control their emotions, strengthening their decision-making in day-to-day classroom scenarios and being a vital component of education success. Because it prevents a teacher from becoming frustrated before realizing their professional potential, the positive reinforcement of emotional intelligence (EI) lowers stress and anxiety levels, improving teacher health and mental well-being, and teaching practice. Figure 4 shows the coping mechanisms of teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement and the emergence of the two themes with their sub-themes: Enhancing self-awareness, Maintaining a positive working environment, and Encouraging personal development.

3.3. The insights are drawn from the Teachers in Reshaping their Lives through Socio-Emotional Intelligence Enhancement—In the process of the in-depth interview, there were many ideas that we can learn from when it comes to the participants' experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement. We face a battle of personal and professional adjustment after the

disruption during the health crisis and trying to provide a learning environment that addresses the needs of learners in the present. In the study, almost all secondary school teachers have experienced the same struggles and challenges in reshaping their lives, the social-emotional adjustments like understanding the emotions of learners, creating a positive learning environment, and promoting wellness for at-risk learners.

3.3.1. Intensifying teacher engagement—This method acknowledges the importance of

teachers' emotional well-being and interpersonal abilities alongside their technical skills

Fig. 4. The emerging themes of the coping mechanisms of the teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement

in creating productive learning environments. Through cultivating self-awareness, empathy, and emotional control, educators enhance not only their job satisfaction and resilience but also their capacity to engage with and assist students effectively. This comprehensive approach to teacher growth fosters a supportive school atmosphere, diminishes burnout, and leads to better student performance by addressing emotional as well as academic needs in classrooms. The study by Dono and Mangila (2021) highlights that teacher engagement significantly influences students' motivation in a subject, revealing a strong connection between these variables. Teacher-student relationships, crucial within the school interpersonal context, are pivotal for students' academic progress, as noted by Martin Collie (2019). Positive teacher-student relationships, as emphasized in secondary school settings with multiple teachers, are shown to have a more enhancing impact on academic development than negative relationships, according to Martin Collie's findings. Findings also showed a cumulative association between students' engagement and increasing the number of positive teacher-student relationships across the range of school subjects in students' academic lives. The engaged teacher adjusts or changes instructions according to the needs of the students in classrooms. Moreover, Teacher self-efficacy, teachers' beliefs in their abilities to organize and execute the courses of action required to produce given attainments, has received much

attention in educational research over the past couple of decades. Research evidence reveals that teacher self-efficacy is related to several positive outcomes, for instance, higher levels of teacher engagement and job satisfaction and lower levels of stress and burnout. Teachers' self-efficacy, engagement, and job happiness have drawn more attention in recent years (Perera et al., 2018). Teachers' engagement at work, which involves positive emotional responses to specific work tasks, may be interpreted as indicators of their perceived capability in a specific domain (Grigg et al., 2018). Enhancing teachers' job satisfaction and engagement is a worthwhile endeavor in and of itself, and it may help minimize expenses related to decreased output, illness, and absence (Perera et al., 2018). Engaged teachers always search for new and innovative ideas for students and implement them in the classroom. Several researchers have affirmed the importance of people who are engaged at work (Harter et al., 2020). Thus, effective teachers are those who are highly engaged and who have an essential role in promoting student motivation and achievement (Dono Mangila, 2021). The role of effective teachers is fundamental in promoting student motivation and achievement. Effective teachers are described as possessing those dispositions that are recurring patterns of thoughts, feelings, or behaviors that result in higher levels of performance as teachers (Hutajulu et al., 2019).

3.3.2. Developing Teachers professionally—Educators with strong emotional intelligence can establish deeper connections with students and create a supportive classroom environment that promotes learning and well-being. Moreover, professional development initiatives focusing on socio-emotional intelligence provide teachers with essential skills to handle difficulties, cope with stress, and sustain resilience

in their professional lives. The main responsibility of a professional teacher is to teach effectively. Due to the constantly changing nature of the teaching profession, changes in this field are endless. The most important agent in the teaching-learning process is the teacher. Students' futures could be made or unmade by their teachers. Faculty development activities like instructional design, instructional delivery,

and understanding of the material, the teacher-student relationship, and the management of the classroom. The twenty-first century has seen an increase in innovative and collaborative teaching approaches (Nairz-Wirth Feldmann, 2019). Teachers' professional development (PD) is crucial to improving student outcomes (Sancar et al., 2021). Research has shown that teachers, after participating in the ongoing CPD program, the participants reemphasized the importance of professional development courses, activities, resources, collaborations, peer learning, self-reflection, and observation in improving teaching skills. They unanimously agreed upon the good changes CPD brings concerning awareness, abilities, perspectives, and ideas (Sancar et al., 2021). Based on the findings of this research, certain aspects of CPD need attention. The quality of training determines its efficacy for educators. Some academics define teacher effectiveness as student achievement, as stated in Stronge's (2018) book. Teachers have a great deal of influence. Therefore, it can be difficult to figure out how to measure their achievements and what kinds of implications they might produce. Because of this, all teachers must possess expected teaching competencies, which can be acquired through Professional activities including lesson planning skills, instructional abilities, and instructional planning skills delivery),

3.3.3. Positive student engagement—The teacher-student relationship promotes student engagement and positive student outcomes in the classroom. This engagement is helpful for teachers. The teachers who input energy to create active and encouraging relationships with their students experience higher levels of well-being and have less emotional burnout and stress. The Teachers who are active in the classroom will display good behaviors, and encourage students to engage them, which, in turn, will increase students' academic achievement.

subject matter expertise, understanding of the material, and rapport building with the pupils (teacher-student relationship), as well as instructional design abilities. Furthermore, some research shows that professional development activities involve teachers' deep reflection on clarifying the teacher's values, mission, and beliefs (Okafor Ezeoba, 2019). School reform is a complex process because it involves encouraging teachers to share a set of practices and beliefs, concepts, resources, and support (AKDEMİR, 2019; Kruse et al., 2018). Additionally, quality professional development is a life-long endeavor (Nasreen Odhiambo, 2018). It includes training, practice, and feedback and provides adequate time and follow-up support. Quality teaching is a function of a sound faculty development program that can enhance the teacher's knowledge and expertise. It can offer a successful and reasonable way to execute best practices and accomplish goals that are set. The intervening factors to effective instruction include teachers' qualifications and professional development activities. A teacher's professional outlook can play a considerable part in creating the ability to become proficient. A teacher's knowledge and enthusiasm for the teaching profession can attract students' interest and increase their academic performance (Padillo et al., 2021).

A teacher who is engaged in the classroom and actively involved in developing healthy teacher-student relations is effective. These findings align with Piovano (2020) that a teacher who shows enthusiasm for improving teaching pedagogy and is responsive to global demands for quality teaching becomes helpful in enriching students' lives. The relationships formed in the classroom and the style of instruction are significantly influenced by the socioemotional competency of the teacher. The effectiveness of education can be increased by teachers who acquire

these skills because they are better able to establish positive relationships with the educational community. Similarly, socio-emotional competency is emphasized in teacher preparation programs since it is thought to be a way to improve the standard of instruction and learning as well as help students develop pro-social behavior (Sporzon Lopez-Lopez, 2021). Teachers who have received training in socio-emotional competencies actually have a big part to play in helping kids acquire these skills so they can have an impact on long-term social development. A number of studies have demonstrated how crucial it is for teachers to have this training in order to decrease absenteeism, dropout rates, and disruptive classroom behavior (Llorent et al., 2020). Additionally, it is important to take into account each student's unique needs. Research has demonstrated that when students develop these qualities, their learning, interpersonal interactions, and academic achievement all improve (Amutio et al., 2020; Lopez et al., 2020). Managing adolescents calls for specialized abilities in the teaching profession. At this point, it is typical to observe violent and disruptive behavior, use of harmful substances, and interpersonal issues with relationships. In addition to stress related to keeping up with pedagogical knowledge and strategies, becoming overworked from correcting homework, classroom diversity, or burnout syndrome, these behaviors also show up in educational centers and classes and become a source of stress for the teacher (Kavita Hassan, 2018). All of these situations call for emotional self-regulation (Martinez-Monteagudo et al., 2019). To preserve mental balance in the midst of all these events, aggressive answers, awareness, and emotional expression are necessary. Simultaneously, one needs to be able to demonstrate social awareness and empathy, especially with adolescents given all the common difficulties. As noted above, a teacher's

socio-emotional competence plays an important role in the relationships established in the classroom and the method of teaching. Teachers who acquire this competence are in a better position to relate positively with the educational community, thereby increasing the effectiveness of education (Piovano et al., 2020). In this same respect, socio-emotional competence is a focus of attention in teacher training, because it is considered to be a means to improve the quality of teaching and learning and the development of students' pro-social behavior (Sporzon Lopez-Lopez, 2021). In fact, teachers trained in socio-emotional competencies have an important role to play in promoting them among students to influence sustainable social development (Santamaria-Villar et al., 2021; Hadar et al., 2020; Zaragosa et al., 2021). Research shows that social-emotional skills support human growth in a variety of areas, including communication, physical development, and cognition. When children are young, people typically expect that all competencies and learning are built on a foundation of social, emotional, mental, physical, and moral skills (Loukatari et al., 2019). As a result, having competence in each of these areas helps children acquire knowledge and grow morals, self-control, empathy, and a positive sense of self. Research has shown that these abilities are supportive elements linked to the growth of personal competencies, and deficiencies in this functional domain are linked to subpar competencies and academic performance (Loukatari et al., 2019). Figure 5 shows the insights drawn from the teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement and the emergence of the three themes with their sub-themes: Intensifying teacher engagement, Developing teachers professionally, and Positive student engagement.

Fig. 5. The insights are drawn from the teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on its findings and future directions in teachers' experiences reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement.

4.1. Findings—The study aimed to explore teachers' experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement. Through their experiences and feelings, we generate new knowledge for everyone who wants to understand the journey of teachers in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement. The data were gathered to examine and give meaningful ideas to generate more practical knowledge that would impact professional life teachers, especially since they were the front liners in delivering quality education. The new learning environment after two years of distance learning brought about paradigm shifts in the teaching and learning process. In teachers' eyes and minds, social-emotional enhancement was essential to providing effective learning. The role of teachers was challenged in providing quality education despite the challenge of providing students with a positive and safe learning environment. Ten (10) secondary school teachers were interviewed. In conclusion, social-emotional intelligence needs to be enhanced. Three themes were revealed when teachers described their experiences in reshaping their lives through socio-emotional intelligence enhancement: self-regulation, working hard on conflict resolution, and challenges in addressing the learning gaps. Therefore, teachers' social and emotional intelligence sets the classroom's tempo. Motivation, self-recognition, social awareness, better general mood, and better management strategies for stress prepare the learner for better academic achievement, and a socio-emotional intelligent teacher can create these all. Educationists consider emotional intelligence tests to be necessary for looking at or predicting the abilities of people. So, this field was very important for improving society and knowing the importance of emotions in our daily lives.

4.2. Implications—This was a more extensive investigation into how teachers have changed their lives by improving their socio-emotional intelligence. Socio-emotional intelligence is the capacity to recognize, use constructively, and regulate one's own emotions to accomplish one's objectives. It also involves recognizing, utilizing, and impacting other people's feelings. The diagram highlights teachers' difficulties in filling in their students' learning gaps. This implies that teachers can better control their emotions and reactions by developing socio-emotional intelligence. Consequently, this could assist them in resolving conflicts with students more skillfully. The face-to-face learning environment after the distance learning implemented during the pandemic posed challenges to the education sector. Learning was done inside the classroom; children were back to the usual setting where they could interact with peers face-to-face—schools designed mechanisms for effectively delivering the curriculum while understanding the social-emotional adjustments of children. However, teachers experienced struggle and adjustment in dealing with the misbehavior of children; they experienced awkwardness and shyness, and some were violent and showed bad temper in interacting with fellow children. Schools ensure learning continuity after the pandemic is managed, and the social-emotional wellness of children is taken care of. The integration

of homeroom guidance into all the lessons in elementary schools was institutionalized. The insights drawn from the experiences of elementary school teachers in dealing with the social-emotional adjustments of learners in this post-pandemic time were integrated routine educational practices, effective monitoring and assessment processes, and professional development planning. These themes can be depicted as teachers providing opportunities for children to

interact with each other positively. They also designed materials for healthy discussions among learners so they can develop self-esteem and camaraderie. All teachers could adopt this system of working towards achieving its goal. The elementary school teachers would consider all those essential themes that give meaningful experiences as the learners continue their social-emotional adjustments.

4.3. Future Directions—While the core themes were found essential to the teachers’ lived experiences on the social-emotional adjustments among children in this post-pandemic time, teachers should formulate appropriate plans and implement adequate strategies to meet the demands of cognitive and affective development of children. They may have a positive mindset, embrace changes, and explore possibilities by providing children with a safe and pos-

itive learning environment. The higher offices and school authorities may work with the teachers to address their challenges as they migrate to the new everyday teaching practices. Necessary resources and relevant training should be provided among teachers to deliver quality education successfully. Similarly, quantitative research across the country may be employed to gain a broader perspective and gain more insights into the varied participants in this study.

5. References

- Abraham, J., & Scaria, J. (2017). Emotional intelligence: The context for successful nursing leadership: A literature review. *Nursing & Care Open Access Journal*, 2(6), 160–164. <https://doi.org/10.15406/ncoaj>
- Agnoli, S., Giacomo, M., Federica, A., & Trombini, E. (2019). The relationship between trait emotional intelligence, cognition, and emotional awareness: An interpretative model. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1711.
- Ajayi, K. O., Onibeju, M. O., & Olutayo, D. O. (2020). Teachers’ qualification, attitude and mastery of content as correlates of students’ academic achievement in economics in lagos state, nigeria. *KIU Journal of Humanities*, 5(1), 315–324.
- Akdemir, Ö. A. (2019). An investigation of the relationship between prospective teachers’ self-efficacy beliefs and their attitudes towards the teaching profession. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 5(3), 156–164.
- Amutio, A., López-González, L., Oriol, X., & Pérez-Escoda, N. (2020). Predicción del rendimiento académico a través de la práctica de relajación-meditación-mindfulness y el desarrollo de competencias emocionales. *Universitas Psychologica*, 19, 1–17.
- Arifin, S. R. M. (2018). Ethical considerations in qualitative study. *International Journal of Care Scholars*, 1(2), 30–33.
- Bardach, L., & Klassen, R. M. (2021). Teacher motivation and student outcomes: Searching for the signal. *Educational Psychologist*, 56(4), 283–297.

- Bergin, C. (2018). *Designing a prosocial classroom: Fostering collaboration in students from prek-12 with the curriculum you already use* (1st). W. W. Norton & Company.
- Bernburg, M., Groneberg, D. A., & Mache, S. (2019). Mental health promotion intervention for nurses working in german psychiatric hospital departments: A pilot study. *Issues in Mental Health Nursing*.
- Botha, R. J. N., & Hugo, J.-P. (2021). Effective mentoring to improve job satisfaction among beginner teachers at south african primary schools. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 6(3), 64–81. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ressat.2021.26>
- Boyatzis, R. (2018). The behavioral level of emotional intelligence and its measurement. *Organizational Psychology*, 9.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101. <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
- Brookshier, K. (2018). *Method vs. methodology: Understanding the difference*. <https://example.com>
- Budzowski, B. (2019). *What is credibility and why do you need to care*. <https://incrediblemessage.com>
- Building research-informed teacher education communities: A ucet framework*. (2019). UCET.
- Butler, L. D., & Cartier, S. C. (2018). Case studies as a methodological framework for studying and assessing self-regulated learning. In D. Schunk & J. Greene (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulated learning and performance* (2nd, pp. 352–369). Routledge.
- Cabigao, J. (2021). Improving the basic writing skills of grade 7 learners in filipino: An action research in filipino language. *Shanlax International Journal of Education*, 9. <https://doi.org/10.34293/education.v9i3.3815>
- Cecchini, J. A., Méndez-Giménez, A., & García-Romero, C. (2018). Validación del cuestionario de inteligencia emocional en educación física. *Revista de Psicología del Deporte*, 27, 87–96.
- Collado, A., Tárraga, R., Lacruz, I., & Sanz, P. (2020). Análisis de actitudes y autoeficacia percibida del profesorado ante la educación inclusiva. *Educar*, 56, 509–523.
- Couper, P. R. (2020). Epistemology. In A. Kobayashi (Ed.), *International encyclopedia of human geography* (2nd, pp. 275–284). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102295-5.10640-7>
- Creswell, J., & Poth, C. (2018). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th). Sage.
- Dono, M. J., & Mangila, B. B. (2021). Mathematics teachers' engagement and students' motivation to learn mathematics. *Journal of Mathematics Education*, 10(2).
- Duru, E. (2021). The nigerian culture and emotional intelligence: Implications for teaching and learning in nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(6), 100–105.
- Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2020). From expectancy-value theory to situated expectancy-value theory: A developmental, social cognitive, and sociocultural perspective on motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 61, 101859. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101859>
- Floreno, F. C. (2021). School learning action cell (slac) among secondary school teachers under new normal. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 9–18. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajess/2021/v21i230502>

- Frenzel, A. C., Becker-Kurz, B., Pekrun, R., Goetz, T., & Lüdtke, O. (2018). Emotion transmission in the classroom revisited: A reciprocal effects model of teacher and student enjoyment. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 110*, 628–639. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000228>
- García, L. (2020). Los saberes y competencias docentes en educación a distancia y digital. una reflexión para la formación. *Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia, 23*, 9–30.
- Glogger-Frey, I., Ampatziadis, Y., Ohst, A., & Renkl, A. (2018). Future teachers' knowledge about learning strategies: Misconcepts and knowledge-in-pieces. *Thinking Skills and Creativity, 28*, 41–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2018.02.001>
- Gregori, E. B., Zhang, J., Galván-Fernández, C., & de Asís Fernández-Navarro, F. (2018). Learner support in moocs: Identifying variables linked to completion. *Computers & Education, 122*, 153–168. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.03.014>
- Grigg, S., Perera, H., McIlveen, P., & Svetleff, Z. (2018). Relations among math self-efficacy, interest, intentions, and achievement: A social cognitive perspective. *Learning and Individual Differences, 53*, 73–86.
- Hadar, L. L. (2020). Rethinking teacher education in a vuca world: Student teachers' social-emotional competencies during the covid-19 crisis. *European Journal of Teacher Education, 43*, 573–586.
- Hattie, J., Hodis, F. A., & Kang, S. H. K. (2020). Theories of motivation: Integration and ways forward. *Contemporary Educational Psychology, 61*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101865>
- Heather. (2020). *Addressing learning gaps when school reopens*. <https://www.quizalize.com/blog/2020/07/28/addressinglearning-gaps-when-school-reopens/>
- Hutajulu, M., Wijaya, T. T., & Hidayat, W. (2019). The effect of mathematical disposition and learning motivation on problem solving: An analysis. *Infinity Journal, 8*(2), 229–238.
- Janis, I. (2018). Strategies for establishing dependability between two qualitative intrinsic case studies: A reflexive thematic analysis. *Journal of Qualitative Research, 34*.
- Juma, A. (2023). *8 types of qualitative research (with uses and benefits)*. <https://www.indeed.com/career-advice/career-development/types-of-qualitative-research>
- Karlen, Y., Suter, F., Hirt, C., & Maag Merki, K. (2019). The role of implicit theories in students' grit, achievement goals, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and achievement in the context of a long-term challenging task. *Learning and Individual Differences, 74*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2019.101757>
- Kavita, K., & Hassan, N. C. (2018). Work stress among teachers: A comparison between primary and secondary school teachers. *International Journal of Academic Research Progress and Development, 7*, 60–66.
- Khatri, K. K. (2020). Research paradigm: A philosophy of educational research. *International Journal of English Literature and Social Sciences, 5*(5), 1435–1440.
- Kim, H. S., & Plester, B. A. (2018). Harmony and distress: Humor, culture, and psychological well-being in south korean organizations. *Frontiers in Psychology, 9*.
- Kleiman-Weiner, M., Sosa, F., Gershman, S., & Cushman, F. (2020). Downloading culture.zip: Social learning by program induction. *Proceedings of the 42nd Annual Virtual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society*.

- Knigge, M., Krauskopf, K., & Wagner, S. (2020). Improving socio-emotional competencies using a staged video-based learning program? results of two experimental studies. *Frontiers in Education, 4*.
- Korstjens, I., & Moser, A. (2018). Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. part 4: Trustworthiness and publishing. *European Journal of General Practice, 24*(1), 120–124. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2017.1375092>
- Kramarski, B., & Heaysman, O. (2021). A conceptual framework and a professional development model for supporting teachers’ “triple srl–srt processes” and promoting students’ academic outcomes. *Educational Psychologist, 56*(4), 298–311.
- Krijgsman, C., Mainhard, T., van Tartwijk, J., Borghouts, L., Vansteenkiste, M., & Aelterman, N. e. a. (2019). Where to go and how to get there: Goal clarification, process feedback and students’ need satisfaction and frustration from lesson to lesson. *Learning and Instruction, 61*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2018.12.005>
- Kruse, S. D., Rakha, S., & Calderone, S. (2018). Developing cultural competency in higher education: An agenda for practice. *Teaching in Higher Education, 23*(6), 733–750.
- Kwang-Ok, P., SungHee, P., & Mi, Y. (2018). Physicians’ experience of communication with nurses related to patient safety: A phenomenological study using the colaizzi method. *Asian Nursing Research, 12*(3), 166–174.
- La Velle, L., & Flores, M. A. (2018). Perspectives on evidence-based knowledge for teachers: Acquisition, mobilisation and utilisation. *Journal of Education for Teaching, 44*(5), 524–538.
- Lalegani, Z., Isfahani, A. N., Shahin, A., & Safari, A. (2019). Developing a model for analyzing the factors influencing interpersonal conflict. *Management Decision*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-08-2018-0857>
- Lawson, M. J., Vosniadou, S., Van Deur, P., Wyra, M., & Jeffries, D. (2019). Teachers’ and students’ belief systems about the self-regulation of learning. *Educational Psychologist Review, 31*, 223–251. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-018-9453-7>
- Lekwa, A. J., Reddy, L. A., & Shernoff, E. S. (2018). Measuring teacher practices and student academic engagement: A convergent validity study. *School Psychology Quarterly, 34*, 109–118. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000268>
- Liu, W., Wang, C. K., Reeve, J., Kee, Y., & Chain, L. (2019). What determines teachers’ use of motivational strategies in classrooms? a self-determination theory perspective. *Journal of Education, 26*(7), 1404–1415.
- López, V., Zagal, E., & Lagos, N. (2020). Competencias socioemocionales en el contexto educativo: Una reflexión desde la pedagogía contemporánea. *Revista de Reflexión e Investigación Educativa, 3*, 149–160.
- Loukatari, P., Matsouka, O., Papadimitriou, K., Nani, S., & Grammatikopoulos, V. (2019). The effect of a structured playfulness program on social skills in kindergarten children. *International Journal of Instruction, 12*(3), 237–252.
- Maamari, B. E., & Majdalani, J. F. (2019). The effect of highly emotionally intelligent teachers on their students’ satisfaction. *International Journal of Educational Management, 33*, 179–193. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-11-2017-0338>
- Mahoney, J. L., Weissberg, R. P., Greenberg, M. T., Dusenbury, L., Jagers, R. J., Niemi, K., Schlinger, M., Schlund, J., Shriver, T. P., VanAusdal, K., & Yoder, N. (2021). Systemic

- social and emotional learning: Promoting educational success for all preschool to high school students. *American Psychologist*, 76(7), 1128–1142. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000701>
- Malejane, A. B., & Diraditsile, K. (2019). Botswana’s education system: A relative analysis with south korean education system. *Journal of Education, Society & Behavioural Science*, 32(2), 1–8.
- Marsh, H. W., Pekrun, R., Parker, P. D., Murayama, K., Guo, J., & Dicke, T. e. a. (2019). The murky distinction between self-concept and self-efficacy: Beware of lurking jingle-jangle fallacies. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111, 331–353. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000281>
- Martin, A. J., & Collie, R. J. (2019). Teacher-student relationships and students’ engagement in high school: Does the number of negative and positive relationships with teachers matter? *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 111(5), 861–876.
- Martínez-Monteagudo, M. C., Inglés, C. J., Granados, L., Aparisi, D., & García-Fernández, J. M. (2019). Trait emotional intelligence profiles, burnout, anxiety, depression, and stress in secondary education teachers. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 142, 53–61.
- Medina, J. A., & Reverte, M. J. (2019). Incidencia de la práctica de actividad física y deportiva como reguladora de la violencia escolar. *Retos*, 35, 54–60.
- Mohd Arifin, S. R. (2018). Ethical considerations in qualitative study. *International Journal of Care Scholars*, 1(2), 30–33. <https://doi.org/10.31436/ijcs.v1i2.82>
- Nadeem, S. (2023). *Coronavirus covid-19: Available free literature provided by various companies, journals and organizations around the world*. https://scimatic.org/show_manuscript/205
- Nairz-Wirth, E., & Feldmann, K. (2019). Teacher professionalism in a double field structure. *British Journal of Sociology of Education*, 40(6), 795–808.
- Nasreen, A., & Odhiambo, G. (2018). The continuous professional development of school principals: Current practices in pakistan. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 40(1), 245–266.
- Neubauer, B. E., Witkop, C. T., & Varpio, L. (2019). How phenomenology can help us learn from the experiences of others. *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 8, 90–97.
- Noble, N., & Heale, R. (2019). Triangulation in research, with examples. *BMJ Evidence-Based Medicine*, 22(3), 67–68. <https://ebn.bmj.com/content/22/3/67>
- Nyirenda, L., Kumar, M. B., & Theobald, S. (2020). Using research networks to generate trustworthy qualitative public health research findings from multiple contexts. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-019-0895-5>
- Okafor, V. E., & Ezeoba, K. O. (2019). Gender inequality in teaching and teacher education programme: Assessment and analysis of anambra state, nigeria. *American Journal of Education and Learning*, 4(2), 184–190.
- Olaoye, A. O. (2020). Emotional intelligence and religion in nigeria: A theoretical exploration. *International Journal of African and African American Studies*, 8(1), 12–25.
- Padillo, G., Manguilimotan, R., Capuno, R., & Espina, R. (2021). Professional development activities and teacher performance. *International Journal of Education and Development*, 9(3), 497–506.
- Paredes, R. (2024). *What is data collection? what you need to know*. <https://safetyculture.com/topics/data-collection/>

- Perrera, H., Granziera, H., & McIlveen, P. (2018). Profiles of teacher personality and relations with teacher self-efficacy, work engagement, and job satisfaction. In *Volume 120*.
- Perry, N. E., Mazabel, S., Dantzer, B., & Winnie, P. (2018). Supporting self-regulation and self-determination in the context of music education. In G. A. D. Liem & D. M. McInerney (Eds.), *Big theories revisited 2: A volume of research on sociocultural influences on motivation and learning*. Information Age.
- Pietila, A., Nurmi, S., Halkoaho, A., & Kyngas, H. (2019). Qualitative research: Ethical considerations. In *Qualitative research* (pp. 49–69).
- Piovano, N., Solodovsky, M., & Pascuali, G. (2020). Competencias socioemocionales y estrés. cómo se relacionan con el rendimiento académico en estudiantes de educación superior. *Revista de Investigación Científica de la Universidad de Morón*, 3, 69–80.
- Piryani, R. M., & Piryani, S. (2019). Conflict management in healthcare [[PubMed]]. *Journal of Nepal Health Research Council*, 16(41), 481–482.
- Poloni, N., Zizolfi, D., Lelmini, M., Pagani, R., Caselli, I., Diurni, M., Milano, A., & Callegari, C. (2018). A naturalistic study on the relationship among resilient factors, psychiatric symptoms, and psychosocial functioning in a sample of residential patients with psychosis. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 11, 123–131.
- Puertas, M., Zurita, O., Ubago, J., & González, V. (2019). Influence of emotional intelligence and burnout syndrome on teachers well-being: A systematic review. *Social Sciences*, 8(6), 185.
- Puertas-Molero, P., Ubago-Jiménez, J., Moreno-Arrebola, R., Padial-Ruz, R., Martínez-Martínez, A., & González-Valero, G. (2018). La inteligencia emocional en la formación y desempeño docente: Una revisión sistemática. *Revista Española de Orientación y Psicopedagogía*, 29, 128–142.
- Qutoshi, S. B. (2018). Phenomenology: A philosophy and method of inquiry. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 5(1), 215–222.
- Ritchie, J., Spencer, L., & O'Connor, W. (2003). Carrying out qualitative analysis. In *Qualitative research practice: A guide for social science students and researchers* (pp. 219–262).
- Safina, A. M., Arifullina, R. U., Ganieva, A. M., & Katushenko, O. A. (2020). Emotional intelligence in teacher's activities. *Journal of History Culture and Art Research*, 9(2).
- Sancar, R., Atal, D., & Deryakulu, D. (2021). A new framework for teachers' professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 101.
- Santamaría-Villar, M. B., Gilar-Corbi, R., Pozo-Rico, T., & Castejón, J. L. (2021). Teaching socio-emotional competencies among primary school students: Improving conflict resolution and promoting democratic co-existence in schools. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 2344.
- Schlegel, K., & Mortillaro, M. (2019). The geneva emotional competence test (geco): An ability measure of workplace emotional intelligence. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 104, 559–580.
- Schoeps, K., Tamarit, A., Barrera, U., & Barrón, R. G. (2019). Effects of emotional skills training to prevent burnout syndrome in school teachers. *Ansiedad y Estrés*, 25, 7–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anyes.2019.01.002>
- Schunk, D. H., & DiBenedetto, M. K. (2020). Motivation and social cognitive theory. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 60, 101832. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2019.101832>

- Segal, J., Smith, M., Robinson, L., & Shubin, J. (2024). *Improving emotional intelligence*.
- Shannon, M., Suldo, S. M., Storey, L. D., O'Brennan, L. M., Shaunessy-Dedrick, E., & Ferron, J. M. e. a. (2019). Identifying high school freshmen with signs of emotional or academic risk: Screening methods appropriate for students in accelerated courses. *School Mental Health, 11*, 210–227. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12310-018-9297-4>
- Siddique, A., Taseer, N. A., & Siddique, M. (2020). Teachers' emotional intelligence and teaching effectiveness: A correlational study. *Ilkogretim Online – Elementary Education Online, 19*(3), 2411–2417. <https://doi.org/10.17051/ilkonline.2020.03.735399>
- Smith, R., Persich, M., Lane, R., & Killgore, W. (2021). Higher emotional awareness is associated with greater domain-general reflective tendencies. *PsyArXiv*.
- Sporzon, G., & López-López, M. C. (2021). Evaluación de la inteligencia emocional y la conducta prosocial y su correlación en alumnado de educación primaria. *Estudios Sobre Educación, 40*, 51–73.
- Stephanou, G., & Oikonomou, A. (2018). Teacher emotions in primary and secondary education: Effects of self-efficacy and collective-efficacy, and problem-solving appraisal as a moderating mechanism. *Psychology, 9*, 820–875.
- Steup, M., & Neta, R. (2020). *Epistemology*. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2020/entries/epistemology/>
- Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers* (3rd). ASCD.
- Team, D. E. (2023). *What is phenomenology in qualitative research?* <https://www.dovetailresearch.com/phenomenology>
- Tenny, S., Brannan, J., & Brannan, G. (2022). *Qualitative study*. StatPearls Publishing. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470395/>
- Valente, S. (2019). Influencia de la inteligencia emocional en la gestión del conflicto en la relación profesor-alumno(s). *Revista de Estudios e Investigación en Psicología y Educación, 6*, 101–113. <https://doi.org/10.17979/reipe.2019.6.2.5786>
- Valente, S., & Lourenco, A. A. (2020). Conflict in the classroom: How teachers' emotional intelligence influences conflict management. *Frontiers in Education, 5*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2020.00025>
- Valente, S., Lourenço, A., & Németh, Z. (2021). School conflicts: Causes and management strategies in classroom relationships. In *Intechopen*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95395>
- Varpio, L. (2018). Using rhetorical appeals to credibility, logic, and emotions to increase your persuasiveness. *Perspectives on Medical Education, 7*, 207–210.
- Vesely-Maillefer, A., Udayar, S., & Fiori, M. (2018). Enhancing the prediction of emotionally intelligent behavior: The pat integrated framework involving trait ei, ability ei, and emotion information processing. *Frontiers in Psychology, 9*, 1078.
- Vesely-Maillefer, A. K., & Saklofske, D. H. (2018). Emotional intelligence and the next generation of teachers. In K. Keefer, J. Parker, & D. Saklofske (Eds.), *Emotional intelligence in education*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-90633-1_1
- Wirihana, L., Welch, A., & Williamson, M. e. a. (2018). Using colaizzi's method of data analysis to explore the experiences of nurse academics teaching on satellite campuses. *Nurse Researcher, 25*(4), 30–34.

- Young, D., & Casey, E. (2019). An examination of the sufficiency of small qualitative samples. *Social Work Research*, 43(1), 53–58. <https://doi.org/10.1093/swr/svy026>
- Zaragoza, M. C., Díaz-Gibson, J., Caparrós, A. F., & Solé, S. L. (2021). The teacher of the 21st century: Professional competencies in catalonia today. *Educational Studies*, 47, 217–237.